

A NOTE ON THE OCCURRENCE OF BEHENIC ACID IN THE OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *PONGAMIA GLABRA*, VENT.*

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The refined oil from the seeds of *Pongamia Glabra* (Honey in Kannada, Karanja and Naktamala in Sanskrit and Sukchain in Hindi) has been subjected to detailed analysis by Sudborough, Watson, and Desai (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1923, 6, 93) and it has been found to contain the following fatty acids:

(i) Myristic acid, (ii) palmitic acid, (iii) stearic acid, (iv) arachidic acid, (v) lignoceric acid, (vi) dihydroxystearic acid, (vii) linolic acid, (viii) linolenic acid and (ix) oleic acid.

While examining the solid which gradually separates out on allowing the crude oil to stand for several days, evidence was obtained for the presence of behenic acid also in the oil.

The solid residue which separates from the oil was repeatedly washed with methyl alcohol to remove the resinous matter. The residue was then extracted with hot ethyl alcohol in a Soxhlet. After all the karanjin (Beal and Katti, *Zentr.*, 1926, II, 596; Limaye, *Proc. Indian Sci. Congress*, 1925, p. 118) was extracted, there remained a residue which was very sparingly soluble in boiling alcohol and was found to be a mixture of zinc salts of fatty acids.

From this the acids were liberated and their methyl esters were distilled under reduced pressure (0.5 mm.), when two principal fractions were obtained.

The free acid obtained from the first of these (b. p. 199-205°/0.5 mm.) on repeated crystallisation from methyl alcohol melted at 78-79°. (Found: M. W., 342.3. $C_{22}H_{44}O_2$ requires M. W., 340). It was, therefore, identified as behenic acid.

The free acid from the second fraction (b. p. 207-212°/0.5 mm.) and residues in the distillation flask on repeated crystallisation from methyl alcohol melted a 74° (Found: M. W., 371.3. $C_{24}H_{48}O_2$ requires M. W., 368.0) and did not depress the m. p. of crude lignoceric acid (m. p. 74°) from natural sources.

Since Sudborough *et al* (*loc. cit.*) have not found behenic acid in the purified oil it is likely that this acid occurs free in the oil and is removed during the process of purification.

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